

THE INFLUENCE OF THE THERMAL TREATMENT ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF APC-2

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ABSTRACT

The morphology and mechanical static and fatigue behaviour in the flexural deformation mode of carbon fibre - reinforced PEEK composites were studied. Specifically, the effect on the above properties of the thermal treatment, comprising melting followed either by cooling to an isothermal crystallization temperatures, or by fast cooling in ice water and annealing, or by fast cooling was investigated. The specimens were made either from prepreg tapes, laboratory formed laminates or commercially available unidirectional composites. Whereas the thermal treatment affected both the matrix morphology and the mechanical properties, the resultant degree of crystallinity did not change. The above effect was assigned to the change in spherulite size and the transcrystallinity. Evidence of transcrystallinity was found and documented.

Key words: PEEK, APC, degree of crystallinity, transcrystallinity, flexural fatigue, spherulite.

INTRODUCTION

The degree of crystallinity of the matrix has a marked effect on the mechanical performance of APC-2 (carbon fibre- reinforced poly(etheretherketone)) composites. This has been confirmed recently by our study of static mechanical properties and of the flexural fatigue behaviour, which showed that a higher degree of crystallinity resulted in significantly improved mechanical properties¹. It is well known, however, that additional microstructural features such as the spherulite size, affect the performance as well². In fact, the present study has been prompted by our preliminary comparative study of the mechanical properties of isothermally crystallized versus quenched-annealed composites of identical nominal degree of crystallinity.

This paper presents the results of a study of the effect of matrix microstructure on the static mechanical properties, on the flexural fatigue life at a constant loading rate and on the fracture surface morphology of APC-2 composites. The results are evaluated in terms of correlating the mechanical performance with the microstructure, and in turn, with the thermal history of the manufacture process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hercules carbon AS-4 fibre reinforced poly(etheretherketone) composites (APC-2) were investigated in the form of prepreg tapes, laboratory formed laminates and commercially available unidirectional composites (ICI Fiberite). Laminates were prepared from APC prepreg tapes of fiber weight content of 68 % and thickness of 0.125 mm. Molding was carried out in a closed metallic mold (50x150 mm²) to produce [(0/90)₂]_s or [(90/0)₂]_s laminates. A number of thermal cycles were employed for laminate processing. For isothermal crystallization in the press the thermal cycle comprised of 7 minutes at 400 °C melting, followed by either cooling to isothermal crystallization at 250 or 310 °C, or by fast cooling in ice water and, consequently, by annealing at 250 °C for 40 minutes, or by fast cooling. Kapton polyimide sheets (Du Pont) coated with Frekote 44 and Frekote HMT release agents (Hysol) were placed between the composite and the steel plates to ensure easy release of the samples. The resultant degree of crystallinities of the specimens were determined by differential scanning calorimetry, using a Mettler TA 400 DSC system at a scanning rate of 20 °C/min. Scanning electron microscopy was used to examine fractured and polished/etched surfaces. Polishing was performed with fine diamond paste (the size of grains was 1 and 1/4 mkm), followed by permanganic etching².

Mechanical testing under, either static or fatigue conditions, was performed in three point flexure with specimens of (50x10x1 mm³) of different thermal histories. A constant ratio of loading span to specimen depth of 40 was used throughout. Static and fatigue testing of the specimens were performed both on a servohydraulic machine (MTS) at a linear loading (extending) rate (ramp function) of 150 cm/min. The fatigue testing was carried out under load controlled conditions at a stress ratio *R* of 0.1, calculated for the tensile side of the flexural specimen. The fatigue loading rollers were installed with a special attachment to prevent in-plane specimen rotation or movement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

It was shown already³ that the mechanical properties of unidirectional APC-2 depended strongly on the degree of crystallinity of the matrix, as determined by the thermal treatment. Namely, the relative values of both the strength and the modulus depended on the thermal cycle according to the order *Q* < *QA* < *AR* (denoting quenched, quenched-annealed and as received, respectively). As this order did not change even for *QA* treatments that resulted in the same degree of crystallinity as that of *AR* material (~ 30 %), the effect of an additional parameter was considered, namely the spherulite size⁴, or its ability to grow until transcrystallinity is formed⁵. In the last case the limiting factor is, in fact, the distance between fibres, that prevents the transcrystallinity development. Actually, scanning electron microscopy confirmed the difference in morphology for polished and etched *AR* and *QA* specimens (Figure. 1), whilst the DSC measurements confirmed that the degree of crystallinity was the same.

Following those observation, fatigue tests were performed with laminate specimens after different thermal treatments. Figure 2 presents the flexural fatigue results expressed in the terms of *S-logN* plots, where *S* is the fatigue stress and *N* is the number of cycles to failure. The common feature for all the trends is the high resistivity of the specimens to fatigue, that probably is determined by the longitudinal fibres. Whereas the measured degree of crystallinity was not affected by the thermal cycle, Figure 2 shows that the fatigue performance was given by the order of *FC* < *FC-A* (250 °C) < *IC*(250 °C) < *IC*(310 °C), where *FC*, *IC* and *FC-A* denote, respectively, fast cooling, isothermal crystallization and fast cooling, followed by annealing. This results, probably, from the fact that the crystallite size follows exactly that order, being highest for the *IC*(310 °C) treatment.

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrograph of etched specimens: (a) AR, (b) Q (X2300)

Another observation concerns the influence of the prepreg tape lay-up on the fatigue behaviour. The ultimate strength values for the specimens with longitudinal layers outside, $[(0/90)_2]_s$, were 30 % higher compared with those with transverse layers, $[(90/0)_2]_s$ (Figure 3). This observation is consistent with the results for $\pm 45^\circ$ angle ply laminates construction⁷.

An additional contribution influenced by the different thermal treatments derives from transcrystallinity, which has been shown to improve significantly the mechanical properties of unidirectional APC-2^{3,8,9}. Figure 4 shows an example of the observed transcrystalline layer, nucleated at and growing from the fibre surface.

The presence and the effect of the transcrystalline layer was examined by a fractographic study of fracture surfaces of the specimens after different thermal treatments. Fractography of the tension side for longitudinal (Figure 5) and transverse (Figure 6) layers after static and fatigue failure modes, respectively, is presented. In specimens after a fast cooling stage, protruded fibers (which are situated in the longitudinal layers) were relatively more exposed (Figure 5b) while the fibers in transverse layers in isothermally crystallized specimens were covered with a fractured transcrystalline layer (Figure 6a) The above observation corroborates the possible effect of transcrystallinity.

Figure 2. Fatigue life diagram of APC [(90/0)₂]_s laminate specimens after different thermal treatments:
 (a) IC(250 °C) and FC-A(250 °C)
 (b) IC(310 °C) and IC(250 °C)
 (c) FC-A(250 °C) and FC

Figure 3. Fatigue life of APC laminate specimens of [(0/90)₂]_s and [(90/0)₂]_s lay-up segmentes

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrograph of etched APC specimen after IC(250 °C) treatment (X2300)

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Longitudinal layers at the tension side of statically failed specimens after different thermal treatments: (a) IC(310 °C), (b) FC-A(250 °C) (X765)

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Transverse layers at the tension side of fatigue failed specimens after different thermal treatments: (a) IC(310 °C), (b) FC-A(250 °C) (X765)

SUMMARY

Fatigue behaviour and morphology of the APC-2 specimens in the form of prepreg tapes, laboratory formed laminates and commercially available unidirectional composites after different thermal treatments were investigated. The specimen morphology was influenced by the thermal treatments, whilst the resultant degree of crystallinity was not. A clear evidence of a transcrystalline layer growing from the fiber surfaces was observed.

Although static and fatigue mechanical behaviour in three-point bending mode were determined mainly by the fibers in the longitudinal layers, the matrix morphology was effective too. The main matrix related factors were the different spherulite size and the transcrystallinity. Fractographic investigation of fracture surfaces after static and fatigue failures confirmed the thermal treatment effect on the fiber/matrix bonding.

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